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A grayscale photograph of a library with tall wooden bookshelves filled with books. A wooden ladder is leaning against the shelves on the left side. On the right edge of the image, there are large, faint letters 'h', 'g', 'f', 'e', 'd' arranged vertically. A dark blue rectangular block is positioned in the bottom left corner, partially overlapping the bookshelves.

OPEN ACCESS

USER GUIDE

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This document draws on a similar project developed by Utrecht University and subsequently adopted by the University of Milan. Its aim is to provide the academic community with an overview of the various forms of open access for both journal articles and books, outlining the advantages and disadvantages, actions required, and the services provided by the relevant institutional units for each type of open access model.

The 4EU+ Alliance supports open access through a range of initiatives and training activities aimed at fostering a shared knowledge base on open science practices, particularly among early-career researchers.

Not all forms of open access are equivalent. A key distinction can be drawn between fee-based models (Gold and hybrid) and those that involve no direct costs for authors (Green and Diamond). Over time, the range of open access pathways has expanded considerably, introducing levels of complexity that were not initially envisaged.

As such, this handy toolkit covers relevant information for researchers seeking to choose an appropriate open access model for both journal articles and books.

The OA models considered for journal articles are the following:

- PREPRINTS
- DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS
- GOLD OPEN ACCESS
- HYBRID/TRANSFORMATIVE OPEN ACCESS
- GREEN OPEN ACCESS

The OA models considered for books are the following:

- DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS
- GOLD OPEN ACCESS
- GREEN OPEN ACCESS

This toolkit was produced by the Performance, Quality Assurance, Assessment, and Open Science Policy Division and will be made available through the Open Science 4EU+ [Zenodo](#) community.

For further questions or in-depth inquiries regarding the several types of open access, please contact one of these e-mail addresses: openscience@unimi.it (University of Milan *La Statale*), oa.buw@uw.edu.pl (University of Warsaw), publications@sorbonne-universite.fr (Sorbonne University), info@ub.uni-heidelberg.de (Heidelberg University).

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JOURNAL ARTICLES

PREPRINTS

A preprint is a research output that has not yet undergone peer-review. It enables research to circulate **prior** to formal publication in a journal and, therefore, to receive timely feedback from peers (in some cases through open peer review tools).

Preprints are typically deposited in dedicated repositories (known as preprint servers), which may be multidisciplinary or subject-specific. Preprint servers typically assign a DOI to the deposited work, which is distinct from the DOI assigned by the journal when the article is formally published.

PROS:

- Depositing a preprint in a repository is free of charge and ensures immediate open access to your work.
- The assignment of a clear timestamp enables authors to establish priority over a discovery or research line.
- Most journals allow the dissemination of a preprint alongside the submission of a scientific paper.
- Some funders allow the inclusion of preprints in CVs, enabling researchers to demonstrate their ongoing research activity regardless of the outcome of the peer-review or publication process.

CONS:

- Not all preprint servers apply rigorous screening procedures before dissemination; consequently, unreliable or low-quality outputs may be encountered.
- Some publishers do not accept manuscripts that have previously been made available as preprints.
- Despite clear disclaimers on preprint servers, external readers may not realise that the work has not yet undergone peer review.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- On-demand training on the use and dissemination of preprints.
- Training on open peer review (to be organised in collaboration with PreReview).
- Support in selecting appropriate repositories and licenses.
- For support, please contact: openscience@unimi.it (University of Milan), oa.buw@uw.edu.pl (University of Warsaw), publications@sorbonne-universite.fr (Sorbonne University), info@ub.uni-heidelberg.de (Heidelberg University).

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Assess the relevance and acceptance of preprints within their discipline.
- Consult directories of preprint servers (e.g. the [AsapBio preprint server directory](#)) to identify the most suitable repository for their work.
- Verify that the target journal permits preprint deposition (e.g. using [Open policy finder](#)).
- Obtain the consent of all co-authors before depositing the preprint.
- Carefully choose the appropriate Creative Commons licence.

JOURNAL ARTICLES

DIAMOND open access

Diamond open access articles are publications that are free of charge for both authors, who do not pay any publication fees, and for readers, who can access the content without subscription or payment.

This model typically relies on dedicated infrastructures provided and supported by academic or research institutions, as well as on the voluntary contribution of editorial boards and peer reviewers. It is often considered one of the most equitable forms of open access.

Diamond open access journals are indexed in dedicated directories, most notably the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#) (DOAJ). Before inclusion, DOAJ conducts a rigorous evaluation of journals' editorial processes, including editorial practices, transparency, and rights management.

An example of a model combining preprint practices with Diamond open access is [Open Research Europe](#), which is currently available exclusively to beneficiaries of European Commission funding.

PROS:

- No direct costs for authors or readers.
- Opportunities for early-career researchers to engage in editorial processes and gain insight into scholarly publishing practices.
- Relatively low operational costs for the institutions supporting the infrastructure.
- Several institutions, including the University of Milan and Heidelberg University, provide Diamond open access publishing services (e.g. university presses) to support journal and book publishing.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- Support for the establishment of Diamond open access journals, including indexing, retrospective digitisation, training in the use of publishing platforms, and guidance on licensing.
- Ongoing monitoring of institutional Diamond open access publishing activities.
- Dissemination of updates through institutional communication channels, including social media.
- Support in the evaluation of publishing venues.
- For support, please contact: openscience@unimi.it (University of Milan), oa.buw@uw.edu.pl (University of Warsaw), publications@sorbonne-universite.fr (Sorbonne University), info@ub.uni-heidelberg.de (Heidelberg University).

CONS:

- Ensuring the long-term sustainability of Diamond open access initiatives can be challenging.
- New initiatives may struggle to gain visibility and recognition, although there is a growing trend of editorial boards resigning from commercial publishers to transition to Diamond open access models.
- In addition to suitable publishing platforms, sustainable operation requires dedicated technical support alongside scientific and editorial expertise.

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Identify Diamond open access publishing options within their discipline, for example by consulting the [DOAJ](#) or contacting institutional support services.
- Consider the possibility of establishing a Diamond open access journal.
- Consider contributing as peer reviewers for Diamond open access journals, thereby supporting the sustainability of this model.

JOURNAL ARTICLES

GOLD open access

Gold open access articles are publications for which authors, or their affiliated institutions pay a fee – commonly referred to as an **Article Processing Charge (APC)** – to ensure that the content is made freely accessible to readers.

Some publishers specialise in gold open access journals, where publication is contingent upon the payment of an APC. Examples include **PLoS, MDPI, and Frontiers**.

Other subscription-based publishers have also introduced gold open access publishing options, such as BioMed Central and SpringerOpen within Springer Nature.

In fully gold open access journals, all publications are **exclusively** funded through the APC model; therefore, alternative publication routes (such as subscription-based access for readers) are not available. APC costs can vary significantly across journals and publishers and have increased in time. These costs are difficult to regulate and control.

PROS:

- Article processing charges (APCs) in fully Gold open access journals are generally lower than those in hybrid journals, although they are increasing.
- Some institutions provide dedicated funding schemes to support APC payments, subject to specific eligibility criteria.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- Guidance on selecting appropriate licences and assessing the cost implications.
- Regular monitoring of APC expenditures by publisher and department (e.g. via [OpenAPC](#) data and institutional reporting mechanisms, such as UNIMI's Open Science Commission's yearly [report](#)).
- Management of institutional APC funds and advisory services for researchers.
- Training on open access publishing options.
- Guidance on identifying and avoiding predatory publishing practices.
- For support, please contact: openscience@unimi.it (University of Milan), oa.buw@uw.edu.pl (University of Warsaw), publications@sorbonne-universite.fr (Sorbonne University), info@ub.uni-heidelberg.de (Heidelberg University).

CONS:

- The Gold open access model represents a significant source of revenue for publishers, which may create incentives to increase publication volumes, potentially at the expense of quality. In recent years, this has contributed to instances of editorial board resignations.
- The APC-based model may exacerbate inequalities between researchers and institutions with differing levels of financial resources.
- The '*publish or perish*' culture has contributed to the growth of predatory publishing practices, many of which rely on APC-based models.

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Assess available publishing options, including potential discounts, and evaluate whether APC-based publication is appropriate.
- Be aware of high APCs and consider cost implications, particularly when public funding is involved.
- Consider alternative strategies, such as publishing in subscription-based venues while ensuring open access through self-archiving of preprint or postprint versions (see Green open access).

JOURNAL ARTICLES

GREEN open access

Green open access refers to the practice whereby authors deposit a version of their work, originally published in a subscription-based journal, in an open access repository. This version typically contains **the same scholarly content as the published article but differs in layout**, as it is usually the Accepted Author Manuscript (AAM), also known as the postprint. Repositories may be institutional (such as the University of Milan's [Institutional Research Archive \(AIR\)](#)) or subject-specific (such as PubMed), and they provide **free public access** to the deposited work. Preprints are also considered a form of green open access. If you cannot share the AAM version, you can use the preprint version.

For articles published by international publishers, authors are usually informed – via tools such as the [Open policy finder website](#) – about which version of their work may be deposited, in which type of repository, and under what embargo conditions. For Italian publishers, these aspects are less standardised. Authors should therefore **carefully review the terms of their publishing agreements, with particular attention to the rights transferred upon signature**, and should seek to retain the right to deposit their work in their institution's repository. It is important to note that, in the absence of a signed agreement, no rights are transferred. While publishers hold rights to the final published version (version of record), they do not necessarily retain rights to the postprint.

Green open access does not involve any cost for authors and readers. However, it requires that articles be made available in a version without the publisher's formatting and may involve an embargo period imposed by the publisher, typically ranging from 6 to 24 months.

In several common law jurisdictions, institutions have adopted rights retention policies, meaning that authors grant their institution a **non-exclusive right** to make their work openly available in an institutional repository without embargo. This prior arrangement takes precedence over subsequent publishing agreements.

In Italy, a similar outcome could be achieved through a reform of copyright law, ideally aimed at guaranteeing secondary publication rights for research outputs.

PROS:

- No costs are incurred by researchers and readers.
- Articles, particularly when deposited in repositories that are highly visible to search engines, circulate widely and achieve strong visibility.
- The University of Milan's publication repository (AIR) is indexed by PubMed and provides links to the Green open access versions of articles. For example, when a full-text version is available in AIR but not in PubMed, users are redirected to the AIR repository via a direct link, thereby providing a valuable service to the global research community.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- The relevant units responsible for open science policies provide advice to researchers on publishers' policies, on identifying and retrieving versions suitable for Green open access, and on negotiating agreements with publishers.
- Some units also monitor Green open access practices within the University and across faculties and departments.
- The relevant units organise regular training sessions on the use of AIR or on copyright-related issues.

CONS:

- Some academic disciplines do not favour the dissemination of postprints (i.e. versions containing the same content as the published article but in a different layout).
- In some cases, identifying the appropriate version (i.e. the version containing the same content but in a different layout) requires additional effort from researchers, which may limit uptake.

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Where possible, authors should obtain, while the article is still in preparation (i.e. prior to publication), a version suitable for deposit in the institutional repository. In some cases, this version is made available by the publisher for a limited time; the corresponding author should therefore ensure timely download in order to retain it for later use.
- When choosing between Gold or hybrid open access and Green open access, authors should assess which option is most appropriate, taking into account that preprints can generally be deposited without an embargo.

JOURNAL ARTICLES

Hybrid/transformational model

Some journals operate under a hybrid model. This means that subscription-based content is published alongside articles that are made openly accessible following the payment of article processing charges (APCs) by authors or their affiliated institutions.

This model is generally **not supported** by research funding bodies, which argue that it can lead to “double dipping”, that is, a single article is paid for twice: firstly through APCs paid to publish the article, and secondly through institutional subscription fees to access the journal in which open access articles are published.

In response to this issue, transformational agreements have emerged. Through these agreements, institutions cover both subscription costs and open access publishing fees within a single contractual framework negotiated with publishers. However, this model is increasingly questioned by funding bodies, as it has not clearly achieved its primary objective of supporting a transition from subscription-based publishing to full open access without generating additional costs.

PROS:

- Researchers may publish in open access in compliance with funder requirements without directly paying APCs or managing related administrative procedures, as these costs may be covered at institutional level.

CONS:

- The hybrid model, in its various forms, entails additional expenditure for institutions, which must cover the costs associated with the “transformation” of journals operated by highly profitable publishers.
- Confidentiality clauses may limit transparency regarding the costs and services included in transformational agreements, making it difficult to assess how funds are allocated.
- Upfront payments made under transformational agreements can reduce researchers’ awareness of the actual costs borne by institutions to ensure access and publication. As a result, researchers may also be less aware of rising costs over time.
- Evidence from studies conducted in the UK by organisations managing transformational agreements suggests that the full effects of the transition may take a very long time to materialise (up to 70 years).

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- Relevant institutional units provide advice on pay-to-publish models and alternative open access publishing options.

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Discuss with colleagues whether hybrid open access is a model worth supporting.
- Be aware of the costs associated with hybrid open access in its various forms.
- Consult [Open policy finder](#) to review journal open access policies, including the costs associated with publishing articles in open access.

BOOKS

DIAMOND open access

Diamond open access is less common in the context of books and refers to a model in which publication is free of charge for authors and access is free for readers.

In this model, institutions typically assume responsibility for the technological infrastructure, provide support for its use, and, in the case of books, also offer editorial services.

The University of Milan provides its researchers and other scholars with a Diamond open access publishing platform: [Milano University Press](#), which publishes books, series, and journals according to this model. It also supports researchers in launching publishing initiatives and in the editorial development of volumes. Similar services are offered by [Sorbonne Université Presses](#) and [Heidelberg University Publishing](#).

These publishing initiatives adhere to international quality standards that enable indexing in the [Directory of Open Access Books \(DOAB\)](#): the “PRISM” label certifies the type of peer review applied.

Textbooks are particularly valuable in this context, as they are made available to students free of charge and can be downloaded in digital formats such as PDF or ePub. University presses may request a modest contribution to cover certain costs. Print-on-demand editions are also typically available at a reasonable price.

PROS:

- The publication process is supported by experienced staff at every stage, from the initial proposal to the final indexing of the volume.
- University presses provide a suitable publishing venue for both educational texts and scholarly monographs.
- The visibility and dissemination of publications are enhanced through their inclusion in major monograph databases.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- Volumes are indexed in major scholarly databases, enhancing their visibility and discoverability.
- Particular attention is given to volumes containing images, especially regarding the management of reuse rights.
- Each volume is assigned an ISBN, while both volumes and individual chapters receive a DOI.
- For support, please contact: openscience@unimi.it (University of Milan), oa.buw@uw.edu.pl (University of Warsaw), publications@sorbonne-universite.fr (Sorbonne University), info@ub.uni-heidelberg.de (Heidelberg University).

CONS:

- Although Diamond open access represents the purest form of open access, in some disciplines the reputation of established publishers remains a significant factor. As a result, authors may prefer traditional publishing venues, even when these involve publication costs and do not allow open access dissemination.
- At present, and in the absence of external funding, services offered free of charge are generally limited to affiliated (in-house) authors. External authors publishing through a university press may therefore be required to contribute to publication costs.

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Explore the available publishing options to identify the most appropriate outlet for their work.
- Attend information sessions organised by university presses and publishers to learn about available services and publishing opportunities.
- Consult colleagues who have previously published through Diamond open access university presses and can share their experience.

BOOKS

GOLD open access

Traditional publishers offer authors the possibility to publish their work upon payment of a fee, commonly referred to as **Book Processing Charges (BPC)**.

The fee typically ranges from approximately €4,000 to €30,000 and varies depending on the publisher's reputation and the type of book.

In the Humanities and Social Sciences, particularly in the context of Italian publishing, it is common practice to pay for the publication of a scholarly monograph. However, this does not necessarily imply that the book will be made available in open access. In such cases, authors are advised to retain key rights for the reuse and dissemination of their work (see *Green open access* section).

BPCs are usually covered by departments, but they may also be paid by authors using grant funding, especially when open access publication is required by funders.

PROS:

- Open access publishing significantly enhances the visibility of publications that might otherwise have a limited presence in bookshops. It enables broader dissemination, global indexing, and access by both academic and non-academic audiences. This is particularly relevant for both English- and Italian-language publications.

CONS:

- Publication costs can be prohibitively high, limiting access to this model for some researchers.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- Relevant institutional units provide support to researchers in selecting appropriate publishers, reviewing publishing agreements, and choosing suitable Creative Commons licences.

- For support, please contact: openscience@unimi.it (University of Milan), oa.buw@uw.edu.pl (University of Warsaw), publications@sorbonne-universite.fr (Sorbonne University), info@ub.uni-heidelberg.de (Heidelberg University).

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Review available publishing options and services, with particular attention to the scope of services covered by the fee (*what am I paying for?*).
- Carefully examine rights transfer agreements. In the case of Gold open access, these should be as limited as possible.
- Choose a Creative Commons licence that facilitates broad reuse and dissemination of the work.

BOOKS

GREEN open access

As with journal articles, Green open access for books involves making a version of the monograph (containing the same content but differing in layout from the published version) available in an institutional repository, typically after an agreed embargo period.

Authors should ensure that their publishing agreements explicitly allow for the reuse of their work in a non-profit institutional repository.

In the Humanities and Social Sciences, particularly in the context of Italian publishing, it is common practice to contribute financially to the publication of a scholarly monograph. However, this does not imply that the book will be made openly accessible. Such contributions, typically ranging from €2,000 to €4,000, are generally considered publication support costs. In these cases, the University of Milan requires the publisher and the author to sign an addendum to the publishing agreement, specifying the conditions under which the full text may be deposited in the institutional repository.

In most cases, the author's version of the monograph may be deposited in the AIR repository following an embargo period, usually ranging from 0 to 18 months.

PROS:

- Green open access enhances the visibility of publications that might otherwise have a limited presence in bookshops. It enables broader recognition and global indexing, reaching both academic and non-academic audiences. This is particularly relevant for both English- and Italian-language publications.

CONS:

- The embargo period may delay the wide dissemination of the work after publication.
- In some disciplines, reuse of the author's version is discouraged due to concerns about consistency in citation practices.
- Publishing agreements may require the transfer of rights beyond those strictly necessary for publication.

SUPPORT SERVICES:

- Relevant institutional units provide support to researchers in reviewing publishing agreements and, where appropriate, in discussing contractual terms with publishers.

WHAT RESEARCHERS CAN DO:

- Carefully review publishing agreements to understand which reuse rights are being transferred.
- Seek support from relevant institutional units when contractual terms are unclear.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAM: Author Accepted Manuscript

APC: Article Processing Charges

AIR: Archivio Istituzionale della Ricerca

DOAB: Directory Of Open Access Books

BPC: Book Processing Charges

COAlition S: international consortium of research funding in collaboration with PlanS

DOAB: Directory of Open Access Books

DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals

DOI: Digital Object Identifier

OA: Open Access

ORE: Open Research Europe

VoR: Version of Record

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